

Lactic Acid Bacteria and Yeasts Associations for Quality Assurance of Sourdough in the Bread Industry

Version 1

Description

This data management plan (DMP) describes the handling of data generated within the research project aimed on the characterization of rye sourdoughs, which reflect Latvia's regional specificity and technological practices.

The project focuses on investigating: the characterization of the microbiota of spontaneous rye and barley sourdoughs from laboratory conditions; characterization isolating the dominant lactic acid bacteria and yeasts and the new associations development; and exploring their application in the development of starter cultures, assessment of starter culture stability and application in a production environment.

The DMP outlines procedures for data collection, processing, quality assurance, storage, documentation, sharing, and long-term preservation to ensure data integrity, security, and compliance with ethical requirements and the FAIR principles.

Research data will include experimental and process metadata (e.g., raw materials descriptions, fermentation parameters, sample identifiers, analytical outputs (physico-chemical characterization of sourdoughs pH, Total titratable acidity, microbial datasets (e.g. CFU counts), sequencing data of lactic acid bacteria and yeast DNS, association stability test results.

At the end of the project, the dataset will be archived in accordance with FAIR principles and deposited in the DataverseLV research data repository, thereby promoting transparency, reproducibility of research, and adherence to Open Science principles.

Funder

Latvian Council of Science | | LCS

Grant

Lactic acid Bacteria and Yeasts
Associations for Quality
Assurance of Sourdough in the
Bread Industry
(1.1.1.9/LZP/2/25/203)

Researchers

Sanita Reidzane (0000-0001-6563-4408)

Organizations

Latvia University of Life Sciences and Technologies

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: [Lactic Acid Bacteria and Yeasts Associations for Quality Assurance of Sourdough in the Bread Industry](#)

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2. Funding

Funding organizations: Latvian Council of Science | | LCS

Grants: Lactic acid Bacteria and Yeasts Associations for Quality Assurance of Sourdough in the Bread Industry (1.1.1.9/LZP/2/25/203)

Project:

3. License

License: CC-BY-4.0

Access Rights: Public

Publication Date: 2026-04-22

4. Templates

Descriptions

DNA sequences of classification-significant genes and species names of rye and barley laboratory conditions sourdoughs

Identification results of yeasts and lactic acid bacteria of rye and barley laboratory conditions sourdoughs – DNA sequences of classification-significant genes and species names.

Template: LCS FARP

Type: Dataset

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

The aim of data collection is to analyze rye and barley sourdough starters prepared under laboratory conditions and collected from production environments, and to characterize the specificity of Latvia. As a result, the rye sourdough starters used in Latvia will be characterized. The isolated cultures will be stored in the laboratory of the Institute of Food. The results will be used to develop new associations of lactic acid bacteria and yeasts in order to create new starter cultures and ensure the quality of existing ones.

Data will be collected by performing analyses of sourdough starters under laboratory conditions. Physicochemical analyses will be carried out (pH, titratable acidity, sugar content). DNA sequencing of genes significant for classification will be performed, based on Sanger sequencing. Consortium NGS sequencing will also be conducted.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Experimental data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

- PDF
- CSV
- XLS
- JPG

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

1

GB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

Prior to the start of the study, relevant datasets and publications on sourdough research were reviewed. No publicly available datasets were identified that would

provide comprehensive and context-specific information on the characterization of Latvian sourdough species to achieve the study objectives. Therefore, it was considered necessary to conduct new data collection.

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

The study data will be useful for researchers of sourdough and substrates from various sources fermentation for the analysis and use of lactic acid bacteria and yeasts in fermentation.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

Yes

Dublin Core

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

Yes

Comment:

When the publication associated with the dataset will be accepted or published.

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

DataverseLV

<https://dv.dataverse.lv/>

DataverseLV was selected as the repository because it is a trusted, institutionally supported platform that ensures long-term preservation and open access to research data in compliance with FAIR principles. It provides persistent identifiers (DOIs) via DataCite, supports rich metadata, and allows for the inclusion of accompanying documentation and code. The platform is aligned with Latvian and European open science policies and ensures data discoverability through international indexing services

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

The dataset will be provided in CSV format, which can be opened with standard spreadsheet software (e.g., Microsoft Excel, OpenOffice Calc) or any text editor, and in PDF format, which can be accessed with widely available PDF readers (e.g., Adobe Acrobat Reader). No specialized software is required.

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

The CSV format is a non-proprietary, machine-readable format that is widely supported by data analysis, spreadsheet, and statistical software, enabling interoperability and integration with other datasets. The PDF format used for documentation is an open standard (ISO 32000) and can be accessed by a wide range of applications. Both formats facilitate long-term accessibility and reuse without dependence on specific proprietary software.

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial 4.0

The dataset will be released under the Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial 4.0 (CC BY-NC 4.0) license to allow free access, sharing, and reuse for non-commercial purposes while ensuring that the original creators are properly credited. This license balances openness with protection against commercial exploitation.

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

The dataset will be deposited in DataverseLV with full metadata, accompanying documentation, and a CC BY-NC 4.0 license. This ensures that third parties can access, understand, and reuse the data for non-commercial purposes even after the conclusion of the project. Long-term preservation guarantees persistent accessibility, and DOI assignment provides a persistent identifier that supports stable referencing over time.

2.4.4 How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?

2040-01-01

The dataset is intended to remain reusable indefinitely. By depositing it in DataverseLV, which provides long-term preservation, DOI assignment, and persistent metadata, the data will be accessible and usable for future research, policy development, and training purposes.

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

After the project's completion, the resources required for long-term data preservation, access, and management — including the repository, its services, and human resources — will be financed by the Higher Education and Science Information Technology Shared Service Centre.

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

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Responsibilities for data management are allocated across all stages, including planning, collection, processing, documentation, storage, and dissemination. Data are collected and validated according to established protocols, while documentation and metadata are developed in parallel with the dataset. Long-term storage and data sharing are handled through an institutional repository, ensuring compliance with FAIR principles and open science policies

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

After the project's completion, the resources required for long-term data preservation, access, and management — including the repository, its services,

and human resources — will be financed by the Higher Education and Science Information Technology Shared Service Centre.

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

Physical access control

All raw data files will be stored on a password-protected external storage drive. Regular automated backups will be performed to prevent data loss.

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

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